

FEATURES OF APPLICATION OF COERCIVE MEASURES TO MINORS AND EXEMPTION FROM LIABILITY OR PUNISHMENT

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According to the current legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, citizens under the age of 18 are recognized as minors. The Constitution of Uzbekistan provides the rights of minors, like all citizens, to education, work, rest, and ownership.

Also, the criminal law defines the responsibility of persons who committed a crime under the age of 18, strictly limited types of punishments assigned according to the criminal law. These types of punishment are specified in Article 81 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and include the following: fine, compulsory community service, correctional work, restriction of freedom, deprivation of freedom. These are assigned depending on the type and nature of the crime, and other types of punishment cannot be imposed on minors. The amount and terms of punishment for juvenile offenders have been significantly reduced.

Exoneration from criminal liability means the completion of criminal legal relations, exemption from punishment means not actually applying criminal punishment to the person who committed the crime. The principle of humanitarianism in our criminal law, the ideas of saving criminal legal repression and its purposeful use are reflected in the institution of exemption from punishment or responsibility.

Exemption of minors from liability or punishment with the use of coercive measures is one of them. Continuing the execution of the sentence may conflict with the task of quickly returning the offender to society.

The existence of the institution of release from criminal punishment or responsibility, to some extent, encourages the moral recovery of prisoners. When releasing a minor from punishment, the person is found guilty by the court, the sentence is not imposed, but a coercive measure is determined. In accordance with the requirements of Article 87 of the Criminal Code, coercive measures are used by the courts instead of criminal punishment to release minors from criminal punishment. Determining the list of coercive measures that can be applied to minors in the law ensures the uniformity of judicial practice in this area. Exemption from criminal punishment with the use of coercive measures is carried out only by the court. Coercive measures have an

educational nature. When applying a coercive measure, the court must aim at the goal of re-education. At the same time, this measure used by the court has the nature of coercion. This is expressed in the execution of the coercive measure only on the application by the court and independent of the discretion of the minor or his legal representative. The implementation of this impact measure is ensured by state authorities. Thus, if the coercive measure has an educational nature according to its structure, it has a mandatory nature according to its execution.

According to the current procedures, if a minor commits a crime punishable by imprisonment for less than five years for the first time, or if he repeatedly commits a crime with a low social risk, the court may release him from punishment. But in this case, the court should consider the issue of coercive measures against him. When releasing minors from punishment and applying coercive measures, the identity of the culprit and the characteristics of the case are taken into account.

When applying coercive measures and exempting from punishment, the court may take into account the identity of the guilty person, the time, place, circumstances, method, form of the crime, the motive and purpose of the crime, and the amount of the damage caused. Coercive measures differ from each other according to their structure. Each measure of influence has its own characteristics in the upbringing of minors. According to Article 88 of the Criminal Code, there are the following types of coercive measures:

- 1) imposing an obligation to apologize to the guilty victim in the manner determined by the court
- 2) imposing the obligation to compensate the amount of damage caused
- 3) placement of a minor in a special educational institution

In conclusion, releasing minors from liability or punishment using coercive measures is listed in Article 88 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and serves to return minors to society by offering a new mechanism in addition to these coercive measures.

The norm on the release of minors from punishment or responsibility with the use of coercive measures is of great importance in ensuring the principle of humanity and solving the issue of responsibility of minors. In this regard, it is justified to consider the issue of release from punishment of a minor who has committed a crime of low social risk again or committed a minor crime for the first time.

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